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Modeling Void Formation And Growth Mechanisms during Co-Cure in Composite Processing

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This lecture is presented in Fond Memory and Tribute to our Fellow Scientist and Friend

Scott White

EARLY VOIDS : Started his career by noting that Voids were not good for Composites in his paper on *Staged Curing of Composites*

TEEN VOIDS: Later he realized that it was too difficult to eliminate them so he came up with the idea to fill them up with resins (self healing)

MATURE VOIDS: Next he found that voids can form the microvascular networks that could be used for transport and enhancement of other composite properties

Co-Cure Process of Sandwich Structures

Equilibrated v/s Sealed Core

Equilibrated (Open) Core

- Core and bag are directly connected
- $P_{core} = P_{bag}$
- P_{core} is the same within all honeycomb cells

Implications

- Model geometry and physics can be simplified

Sealed (Closed) Core

- Core and bag are separated by permeable skins
- $P_{core} = f(K, \Delta P, t, T \dots)$
- P_{core} can vary between honeycomb cells

Implications

- Model geometry and physics are more complex.

Physical Mechanisms during Co-cure

Facesheet Consolidation

- Flow/compaction over core
- Prepreg/adhesive mixing

Adhesive Bond-Line Formation

- Fillet formation
- Prepreg/adhesive mixing

Bond-line Porosity Evolution

- Void growth
- Void transport

Core Pressure Evolution

- Gas flow in/out of core
- Volatile release
- Thermal expansion

Effect of Pressure and Temperature Cycle on Void Dynamics (Open Core)

- Equilibrated/Open Core Co-cure

Effect of Pressure and Temperature Cycle on Void Dynamics (Sealed Core)

➤ Sealed/Closed Core
Co-cure

Process Inputs and Material Models

Process Development Facesheet Consolidation Model

Material Properties
Cure Cycle

Permeability
Fiber Volume Fraction
Resin Pressure

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Process Development

Core Pressure Prediction

Bond-line Fillet Formation Model

Material Properties
Cure Cycle

Core Pressure

Material Properties
Cure Cycle

Fillet Height
Adhesive Thickness

Process Development

Bond-line Porosity Evolution

- Void Growth Mechanisms
- Diffusion-induced growth prediction
- Void Growth Model
- Porosity Evolution

Bond-line Porosity

The central diagram shows a bubble with a liquid shell. The bubble radius is R , and the shell thickness is s . The concentration at the bubble interface is C . The diffusion flux is $\dot{m}_{diffusion} = AD\frac{\partial C}{\partial r}$. The concentration at the bubble interface is given by Henry's Law: $C = K_h P_b$ (Henry's Law) Concentration at bubble interface. The concentration at the liquid shell is $C_{(r,t=0)} = C_0$. The partial differential equation for concentration is $\frac{\partial C}{\partial r} = 0$ at $r=R$.

Two graphs show the evolution of porosity over time. The left graph plots porosity (0 to 4.5) vs Time (s) (0 to 400) for different temperatures (20, 40, 60, 80, 100, 120, 140, 160, 180, 200 °C). The right graph plots porosity (0 to 100) vs Time (s) (0 to 100) for different temperatures (20, 40, 60, 80, 100, 120, 140, 160, 180, 200 °C).

Micrographs on the right show cross-sections of the bond-line with visible porosity.

Coupling Various Models to Simulate the Void Dynamics in Co-Cure Process

Process Inputs

Material Properties

- Prepreg Facesheet
- Adhesive
- Core

Cure Cycle

- Autoclave Temperature
- Autoclave Pressure
- Vacuum Bag Pressure

Process Development

Facesheet Consolidation

- Material Properties
- Cure Cycle

Bond-line Fillet Formation

- Material Properties
- Core Pressure
- Bond-line Porosity

Void Transport

Facesheet Gas Permeability

Void Transport

Pathway Creation

Bond-line Porosity

- Material Properties
- Core Pressure
- Fillet Shape

Core Pressure

- Volatile Generation
- Facesheet Consolidation
- Bond-line Porosity

Pathway Creation

Co-Cure Simulation Tool: SANDWICH

Step1 : Defining Cure Cycle and Materials

Selectable Materials

Porosity Model inputs

Cure Cycle Graphs

Process Description:
Applied Pressures
(Autoclave, Vacuum)
and
Temperature

Void Growth
Stability Map

The screenshot displays the SANDWICH software interface. On the left, there are three panels for material selection: 'Select Prepreg' (Hexcel-HexPly 8525/PVW, 4 plies), 'Select Adhesive' (Henkel-Loctite 9630 AERO N800), and 'Select Core' (1/8" size). Below these are 'Porosity Model inputs' including 'Dissolution Based' model, 'Initial Size of Bubble [m]' (0.0001), and 'Initial Porosity [1]' (0.01). The main area contains two graphs: 'Cure Cycle Temperature' and 'Autoclave/Bag Pressure'. A table titled 'Read Process Data File' is also present.

Time [s]	Temperature [C]	P autoclave [Pa]	P bag [Pa]
0	20	100000	0
3600	20	100000	0
3800	20	200000	100000
6300	120	200000	100000
9900	120	200000	100000
10100	120	377000	239000
10700	200	377000	239000
18000	200	377000	239000

SANDWICH Co-Cure Simulation

Step2 : Inspect/Modify the Material Behavior

Sandwich Co-Cure Simulation

Step3 : Simulation Results

Simulation Controls

Simulation Type:
Open / Sealed Core

Framework of the Process Model

Summary and Conclusions

- Models to predict prepreg facesheet consolidation, adhesive bond-line fillet shape, and bond-line porosity were developed.
- In addition to pressure and temperature, influence of parameters such as facesheet air permeability, core pressure and adhesive fillet shape on the bond-line porosity was explored.
- A stability map was created and its interaction with the selected cure cycle was demonstrated to help design the processing cycle
- A simulation was created to design the pressure and temperature cycles for the co-cure of sandwich structures

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